

Third World Quarterly - Decision on Manuscript ID CTWQ-2021-0425.R1

 De Third World Quarterly <onbehalf@manuscriptcentral.com>
Destinatario <roser@ugr.es>
Responder a <CTWQ-peerreview@journals.tandf.co.uk>
Fecha 2022-08-25 17:58

25-Aug-2022

Dear Dr Manzanera-Ruiz,

I hope this email finds you well. Thank you for your continued patience throughout the peer-review process.

Your manuscript "Women's approaches doing business and entrepreneurship in Uganda", which you submitted to Third World Quarterly, has been reviewed. The referees' comments are included at the bottom of this email.

The reviews are in general favourable and suggest that, subject to these **minor revisions**, your paper may be suitable for publication.

We look forward to receiving your revision.

When you revise your manuscript please highlight the changes you make in the manuscript by using track changes, coloured text or highlights.

**** Important Notice ****

Final versions must not exceed 9,500 words including title pages, abstracts, and bibliography.

To start the revised manuscript, please click on the link below:

***** PLEASE NOTE: This is a two-step process. After clicking on the link, you will be directed to a webpage to confirm. *****

https://mc.manuscriptcentral.com/ctwq?URL_MASK=f539d70b8cb3453bb4a75d2cccf5f4bd

This will direct you to the first page of your manuscript. Please enter your responses to the comments made by the reviewers in the space provided and document any changes made.

This link will remain active until you've submitted your revised manuscript. If you begin a revision and intend to finish it at a later time, please note that your draft will appear in the "Revised Manuscripts in Draft" queue in your Author Centre.

IMPORTANT: Your original files are available to you when you upload your revised manuscript. Please delete any redundant files before completing the submission.

We are trying to facilitate timely publication of manuscripts submitted to Third World Quarterly so your revised manuscript should be uploaded by 15-Sep-2022. Please be aware that timezones can affect submission deadlines.

Once again, thank you for submitting your manuscript to Third World Quarterly and we look forward to receiving your revised paper.

Best wishes,

Madeleine

Dr Madeleine Hatfield
Managing Editor, Third World Quarterly
On behalf of the Academic Editors
CTWQ-peerreview@journals.tandf.co.uk

Reviewer(s)' Comments to Author:

Referee: 1

Comments to the Author

The authors put a lot of effort and thought into revising the paper. In my view, no further revisions are needed apart from thoroughly proofreading and formatting the paper. Minor comment: I would leave out references to authors in the abstract. I look forward to seeing this published.

Referee: 2

Comments to the Author

Overview

I wish to congratulate the authors for their paper which seeks to tackle a topical issue on women entrepreneurship in Africa. The paper attempts to build cumulatively on the body of existing literature on this research theme. However, there are some concerns which the authors need to address. The details are provided below.

The title

The title "Women's approaches doing business and entrepreneurship in Uganda" does not read correctly for me. Neither does it fully reflect the contents of the paper. The authors should revisit it.

The abstract

An abstract should provide enough information to allow a reader to judge whether the piece is of interest to them. It needs to emphasise the research setting, purpose, methodology, major findings, and research implications. Considering this, the authors should double-check their abstract to ensure that it fits the guidelines outlined above.

Introduction section

The research questions are stated clearly in this section, but the build-up to them is not compelling. How did the researchers come up with their research questions? What are the theoretical and practical implications of dealing with the research questions? Why did they choose a post-colonial African perspective to frame their research? In light of the preceding issues, I believe the authors have been unable to persuasively motivate/justify their study. In this section, the narrative is also fragmented. I recommend that they follow the guidelines in Swales' C.A.R.S model (<https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/CARS>) to improve their presentation.

Literature review section

This section presents and reviews some recent and relevant literature. However, I am concerned about the organisation and presentation of the review. Why didn't the authors devote a section to the guiding theory, namely, the post-colonial African perspective? In addition, the literature review section should be narrowed down to the literature on the culture-female entrepreneurship nexus. "In this study, we contextualise female entrepreneurship in Uganda as influenced by the socioeconomic environment, social networks, and family ties," the authors write at the end of the LR section. How did they come to that conclusion when their review yielded no evidence to back up their claim? The literature review also fails to reveal any knowledge gaps that their study will fill.

Methods section

A qualitative approach is fully appropriate for the study, but the authors need to explain why. The research design and methods chosen are appropriate for the study. The details of the target population and sampling procedure followed are comprehensive.

- The statement in line 55 page 9 which reads "using a qualitative approach through participant observation" is not accurate and needs to be revised.
- details of the research instrument used need to be provided.
- measures taken to safeguard the credibility of the findings also need to be explained.
- data collection approaches well-articulated? Sensible?
- the analytic approaches are not articulated. Did the authors use content analysis? Thematic analysis?

Results section

- the steps involved in the data analysis are not explained and the strategies are not justified.
- to some extent, the presented results are relevant to the research question.

Discussion section

The authors attempted to discuss their results and link them to extant literature but this was all compressed to the conclusions section. The discussion, however, does not come out convincingly on the theoretical and practical implications of the results. Neither does it indicate the limitations of the study and any suggestions for further research.

Conclusion section

While the authors correctly highlight the study's key findings, they use this section inappropriately to link the results to previous studies. The discussion of the findings should be done in the discussion section.

Other issues

- The appropriate referencing convention was adhered to.
- Very few linguistic issues were noted.

Decision

The authors need to revise the paper substantially to improve its quality before it can be published in a high-quality journal such as The Third World Quarterly. Hopefully my comments help in that regard. All the best to the authors.